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SSI Machine Learning

Empowering researchers
through digitally enhanced
research

Small-Scale
Initiatives 2022c

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About this call

Purpose of this call

The Small Scale Initiative (SSI) Machine Learning call for proposals aims to help researchers in any discipline who want to benefit from machine learning (ML) techniques, but who need additional expertise in applying these methods. We offer in-kind support for a collaborative project based on a use case, in which we will help you choose, develop and apply ML techniques. A successful proposal should formulate a clear research problem and describe how you expect ML techniques to contribute to solving it.

What can be applied for?

Each project involves support provided by our research software engineers (RSEs), employees of the eScience Center who combine broad disciplinary knowledge with high-level digital expertise. Their method of working is collaborative: together with you, the RSEs form a research team that will share knowledge, explore possible approaches and develop digital solutions.

The RSEs will offer advice and support for the duration of the project to help achieve the desired results, and will co-author publications with you. In addition to their specific focus on the development of advanced research software, RSEs at the eScience Center help you interpret the results of your research and contribute to making the tools and methods that emerge from the project (re)usable for the wider research community.

Expected project deliverables include a selection of the following:

- tutorials, examples and documentation of methods and research software
- blog posts and/or white papers
- one or more research articles in an academic journal
- published open-source research software or code

Available projects

The call makes available in-kind support by allocating eScience Center RSEs to the awarded projects. You can apply for a maximum of 768 hours of support (0.5 FTE, 6 months of RSE). A total of 5 projects can be awarded in this call.

The RSEs will work on the project for a specific period. Projects are expected to start in 2023; all projects should be completed by December 2024 at the latest. The actual start and end dates depend on the availability of RSEs and will be determined in consultation with you. The project duration is expected not to exceed more than one year.

Validity of this call

This call for proposals is valid for proposals submitted before the deadline of 1 November 2022, 14:00:00 CET, until the Directors Team of the Netherlands eScience Center has taken the final decision, as specified in the assessment procedure.

About the Netherlands eScience Center

The Netherlands eScience Center is the national centre for innovative software solutions in academic research, established as an independent foundation to advance digital technologies. Its vision is to establish a robust research community, in which all investigators in all domains are able to exploit advanced digital technologies and research software to answer innovative research questions, keeping the Netherlands at the forefront of cutting-edge international research. The office of the eScience Center is located in Amsterdam; RSEs perform their project activities at the office, remotely and at project locations.

The Netherlands eScience Center regularly organizes workshops in our Digital Skills Programme. Our project partners are encouraged to participate in these workshops.

Open science, reproducibility, and sustainability

Collaborating with the eScience Center requires applicants to support the use and development of standards-based open-source solutions.

To support the wider research community while ensuring the reproducibility, transparency and integrity of research activities, all output from eScience Center projects adheres to open science principles. Publication are made available as open access, data is offered as FAIR data and source code is made publicly accessible on a software development platform (e.g. GitHub), while all software and documentation use permissive open-source licences.

Guideline for applicants

Who can apply?

Each proposal is to be formally submitted by a single named researcher or 'lead applicant' (henceforth LA). The LA

1. must be in possession of a PhD;
2. must be employed by a Dutch research performing organization (Appendix A) for the duration of the project;
3. should have affinity with (or a willingness to learn to apply) digital methods;
4. should be free to spend a reasonable amount of time on the proposed project (to be specified on the application template);
5. should actively support dissemination activities relevant to the project.

The LA may submit only one proposal in that capacity in this call. By the submission deadline, the LA may not be the Lead Applicant or Principal Investigator in an on-going project of the eScience Center originating from eScience Center calls.

Preparing an application

Proposals must use the application template “Application template Small-Scale Initiatives Machine Learning” available on the eScience Center website. Applicants should take note of the following requirements:

Software and data

In case the proposal builds on existing software, or critically depends on the availability of a dataset, the research software or dataset must be available for use from the start. The software should be of sufficient quality to allow its use for research and collaborative development. If you are unsure whether your software is suitable, please contact the eScience Center.

Submitting the application

Proposals must be submitted by e-mail. The deadline for submission is **1 November 2022, 14:00:00** (CET). Please send the completed application template to: open-ssi-call@esciencecenter.nl

Assessment procedure

Submissions will be reviewed by experts from the Netherlands eScience Center together with experts representing the Machine Learning field. To be eligible for funding, an application must have the minimal overall qualification ‘good’.

Evaluation criteria are:

- Research question 40%
- Digital solutions 40%
- Research sustainability 20%

Lead applicants will be informed on the decision by email by mid-December 2022. Applicants will receive a short motivation on the decision. It is not possible to correspond about the decision

Timetable

9 September 2022	Call publication / start of submission period
1 November 2022	Submission deadline
8 November 2022	Eligibility check
December 2022	Final decision
1 January 2023	Project should start after this date
31 December 2024	Project should end before this date

Contact details

If you have specific questions about this call for proposals or the assessment procedure, please contact:
our Programme Manager (open-ssi-call@esciencecenter.nl)

Appendix A – Eligible organisations

1. Universities

Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam
Open Universiteit Nederland
Protestantse Theologische Universiteit
Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen
Rijksuniversiteit Groningen
Technische Universiteit Delft
Technische Universiteit Eindhoven
Theologische Universiteit Apeldoorn
Theologische Universiteit Kampen
Universiteit Leiden
Universiteit Maastricht
Universiteit Twente
Universiteit Utrecht
Universiteit van Amsterdam
Universiteit van Tilburg
Universiteit voor Humanistiek
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
Wageningen Universiteit en Researchcentrum

2. University Medical Centers

Amsterdam UMC (locations: AMC and VUMC)
Erasmus MC
Leiden UMC
Maastricht UMC+
Radboud UMC
UMC Groningen
UMC Utrecht

3. KNAW institutes

Hubrecht Instituut voor Ontwikkelingsbiologie en Stamcelonderzoek

Huygens ING

Internationaal Instituut voor Sociale Geschiedenis (IISG)

Koninklijk Instituut voor Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde (KITLV)

Meertens Instituut

Nederlands Herseninstituut

Nederlands Instituut voor Ecologie (NIOO)

NIOD Instituut voor Oorlogs-, Holocaust- en Genocidestudies

Nederlands Interdisciplinair Demografisch Instituut (NIDI)

Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute

4. NWO institutes (NWO-I)

AMOLF - Physics of Functional Complex Matter

ARCNL - Advanced Research Center for Nanolithography

ASTRON - Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy

CWI - Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica

DIFFER - Dutch Institute for Fundamental Energy Research

Nikhef - Nationaal instituut voor subatomaire fysica

NIOZ - Koninklijk Nederlands Instituut voor Onderzoek der Zee

NSCR - Nederlands Studiecentrum Criminaliteit en Rechtshandhaving

SRON - Netherlands Institute for Space Research

Attachments

1. Terms conditions eScience Center
2. IP conditions